

HOSPITALITY SERVICES IN TOURISM AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the development and prospects of the hospitality industry in Uzbekistan, the use of a marketing complex, the expansion of the range of hospitality services and the development of additional tourist services, and the problems related to marketing activities in hotels.*

Keywords: *Tourism, hospitality, service, business, industry, opportunity.*

INTRODUCTION

Tourism and hotel business have a special place in the service sector. Therefore, as the President noted, "It is inevitable that the development of this sector will make a huge contribution to the economic and social development of our country by attracting a lot of foreign tourists to our country, and most importantly, by providing large foreign exchange earnings."

The existence of both the necessity and the opportunities for the tourism and hospitality business, the continuous increase of the requirements for it, imposes the requirements to strengthen the economy and increase the efficiency of the tourist complexes that carry out these types of activities, to organize the management tools that serve this, such as tourism marketing in accordance with today's requirements. This demand, in turn, necessitates deep research of the problems of economic development and efficiency improvement of tourist complexes, as well as theoretical, organizational and methodological issues of marketing in them.

These characteristics of the tourist product have a great influence on the content of tourism marketing. Based on this, tourism marketing is a set of methods and methods of organizing the promotion of tourist services in order to meet the demand for recreation and recreation in the tourist market.

Research methodology

Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results

The hospitality industry provides a complex of services to consumers, among which hotel service occupies the main place. From a business point of view, a hotel is an enterprise that has certain consumer characteristics and is able to satisfy the needs of customers, producing and providing services. The improvement of service marketing in the hospitality industry is included.

To achieve this goal, several tasks were set in the work:

1. Development and prospects of the hospitality industry in Uzbekistan.
2. Application of the marketing complex in the field of hospitality.
3. Expanding the range of hospitality services and development of additional tourist services.
4. Analysis of the main directions and results of marketing activities in the hotel;
5. Show problems related to marketing activities in the hotel;
6. Show ways to improve marketing activities in tourist enterprises.

The hospitality industry is one of the fastest growing sectors of the industry. "Hospitality industry is a business sector consisting of services that rely on the principles of hospitality, characterized by friendliness and openness to guests." In this regard, the hospitality industry can be defined as the names of various activities related to receiving and serving guests. The word "guest" is as important in the hospitality industry as it is in the service industry. According to the applicable legal norms and the rules existing in the practice of the hospitality industry, the term "guest" is similar to the concepts of "consumer" and "customer".

Marketing in the hospitality industry is formed on the basis of the experiences of industrial and commercial companies, has absorbed the achievements of general marketing theories and its practical application. At the same time, marketing in the hospitality industry has a number of characteristics that allow it to be studied as a specific type of activity.

The hotel business consists of several departments offering accommodation, catering, travel arrangements, car rental, dry cleaning, hair salon, massage room, fitness centers. The most important of these are catering, accommodation and delivery services.

The essence of the accommodation service is that, firstly, guests are given a special place for use (hotel rooms) and secondly, services performed directly by the hotel staff are provided.

Food delivery services consist of a complex of various processes: production (food preparation in the kitchen), sales (sale of ready-to-eat products, alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages), service (service to guests by waiters in restaurants, cafes and hotel rooms).

Figure 1.

Tourist services are a set of activities aimed at meeting and providing the needs of tourists and excursionists, and they should meet the goals of tourism, the nature and orientation of the tourist service, and should not be against universal principles. According to the definition of the state standard, tourist services are the products of the activities of tourism organizations engaged in satisfying the needs of tourists.

Services in general are a special type of intangible commodity. Service occurs directly in the consumption process and does not exist separately. This is the main difference between a service and a product. In addition, the goods are brought to the consumer, and in the case of tourist services, the consumer is taken directly to the place where the service occurs. Therefore, the production and sale of tourist services is not governed by the laws related to the sale of material goods, but by a different set of laws.

In the tourism service, the concept of export and the law are different. According to some sources, according to the traditional option, the services of the head of the tourist group in foreign countries and the services of the bus driver sent to work in a foreign country are related to the export of tourist services.

The tourist service includes booking services, transportation, accommodation and all other formalities, all types of transportation, transfers, meals, excursions and attractions, medical examination and insurance, translation services, meetings, etc.. Services may include the services of a group leader and a guide-interpreter.

Each network's range of services is different, determined by the application, and each service has many other elements included.

If we consider tourism, according to general principles, every tourist package will have at least two types of services, which are: transportation and accommodation service package. These are called the main tourist services (two). According to experts, there are more than 400 additional tourist services. Except for the two (main) types of services mentioned above, all other services are additional tourist services. Even catering and excursion services. Services may be extended by the organizer at the request of the tourist, or this may be determined by the organizers at the choice of the tourist. The latter is preferable, because overall prices are reduced to a minimum level according to the principles and values of competition. This leads to the minimization of the package of services.

It was found that successfully organized marketing and expenses spent on bringing the tourist product to the international market will return to the government in the form of economic and political dividends. Comprehensive studies in many European countries show that for every additional dollar spent by each tourist, 50 cents goes to the government coffers in the form of income taxes.

The "Hotel Association" of Uzbekistan should have its own page on the Internet, where video tapes about all tourist products of Uzbekistan and the addresses of tour operators and tourist agents should be displayed. In addition, the Association should have two employees at its headquarters in Tashkent who can speak English fluently and who can provide positive information about Uzbekistan to the international media. The biggest problem in developing a marketing plan for Uzbekistan is the lack of quick and accurate information about the existing market. The Department of Analysis and Economics of the national company "Uzbekturizm" does not yet have such experience. The main focus in this regard is the introduction of a system of timely delivery of information about tourists coming to Uzbekistan together with airports and immigration services. Thanks to the membership of the BTT Executive Committee, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to have information about the situation in the international tourist community. Apart from that, it would be appropriate to involve international diplomatic missions in collecting information about what is happening in major tourist countries. The availability of direct flights to these countries is an important factor when the national company "Uzbekturizm" opens its representative offices abroad. The foreign representative offices of many touristic organizations make it their main task to participate in market activities and work with customers on the spot, providing them with relevant information. "

Repair works of four airports in Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Khiva are being completed in Uzbekistan.

In world tourism today, the private sector controls 90% of the world's tourism infrastructure.

The main directions of development of investment allocation for hotels are as follows:

- to see medium-class (three-star) hotels that are not large (with an average of 200 beds). This allows for the full use of existing capabilities, easier financing due to its small size, lower operating and management costs, and manageability even for medium-level trained professionals.

- renovating the existing hotels and bringing them up to international standards. According to the results of the research, it is appropriate to spend almost 50% of all capital for this direction.

- Development of the infrastructure of motels, airports, car dealerships, development of motor vehicles along the Tashkent-Samarkand-Khiva route. As a result, the level of efficiency of these directions increases almost twice.

- as a result of allocating investments to sports facilities and the development of more than 250 religious objects, the number of visitors to Uzbekistan from all over the world for religious tourism may increase 10-12 times.

- investments can be made by a number of large banks and companies of the world.

- internal resources should be the main source of hotel investment. First of all, it is necessary to increase the efficiency of using existing hotel facilities: specialized hotels, as well as places for various offices.

- Combining the efforts of all hotel infrastructure owners will help to increase the occupancy of hotels, increase the number of tourists staying in them, and increase the categories of tourists. For this purpose, it will be necessary to organize the Association of national tourist organizations, including hotel organizations. One of the important aspects of effective use of limited foreign exchange funds is the centralized use of all foreign exchange funds for tourism. For this, it will be necessary to establish a unified centralized currency fund of Uzbekistan with the funds received from hotels and tourist organizations and direct the funds in it to solve national problems of international tourism development.

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